

THE ROLE OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ENHANCING TOURIST EXPERIENCE

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Abstract. *This study examines the role of HRM (human resource management) in enhancing service quality and tourist satisfaction in tourism industry. The main objective is to examine the relevance of HRM practices, such as employee training, motivation, and management support to employee performance and overall tourist experience.*

Quantitative research was conducted in city Samarkand, Uzbekistan Republic. The target audience consists of hospitality sector employees and guests/tourists. For this study, purposive and convenience sampling methods were used. Totally two surveys were conducted: a questionnaire for hospitality sector employees and separate questionnaire for tourists. The former collected 65 responses, while the later collected 67 responses. Collected data were analysed using SPSS software.

The findings showed that HRM practices significantly influence the motivation of employees to deliver high-quality service to the guests. Moreover, results revealed that there is a significant relationship between employee behaviour, service quality and tourist satisfaction. The study concludes that effective HRM can enhance the quality of service and , consequently, influence the tourist experience in tourism industry.

Keywords: *Human Resource Management (HRM); Tourist Experience; Tourism Industry; Hospitality Sector; Employee Performance; Customer Satisfaction*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqot turizm sohasida xizmat korsatish sifati va sayyohlarning qoniqishini oshirishda HRM (inson resurslarini boshqarish) rolini o'rganadi. Asosiy maqsad HRM amaliyotlarning, masalan, xodimlarni o'qitish, motivatsiya va boshqaruvni qo'llab-quvvatlashning xodimlarning ishlashi va umumiy sayyohlik tajribasiga mosligini o'rganishdir.*

O'zbekiston Respublikasining Samarqand shahrida miqdoriy tadqiqot o'tkazildi. Maqsadli auditoriya mehmondo'stlik sohasi xodimlari va mehmonlar/sayyohlardan iborat. Ushbu tadqiqot uchun maqsadli va qulaylik namunalarini olish usullari qo'llanildi. Jami ikkita so'rovnoma o'tkazildi: mehmondo'stlik sohasi xodimlari uchun sio;rovnoma va sayyohlar uchun alohida so'rovnoma. Birinchisida 65 ta javob to'plangan, ikkinchisida esa 67 ta javob to'plangan. To'plangan ma'lumotlar SPSS dasturi yordamida tahlil qilindi.

Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, HRM amaliyotlary xodimlarning mehmonlarga yuqori sifatli xizmat ko'rsatishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Bundan tashqari, natijalar xodimlarning xulq-atvori, xizmat ko'rsatish safati va sayyohlarning qoniqishi o'rtasida muhim bog'liqlik borligini ko'rsatadi, Tadqiqot samarali HRM xizmat ko'rsatish sifatini oshirish va natijada turizm sohasidagi sayyohlik tajribasiga ta'sir qilishi mumkin degan xulosaga keldi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Inson resurslarini boshqarish; Turistik tajriba; turizm sohasi; Mehmondo'stlik sohasi; Xodimlarning ishlashi; Mijozlar qoniqishi.*

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research history

A large qualified staff is needed to run labour-intensive and adaptable tourism industry. It significantly contributes to the world economy, by creating millions of jobs worldwide in a different sector related to the tourism. The human factor plays a crucial role in the tourism and hospitality sectors. Customer impression, satisfaction, and the destination's overall image is widely influenced by the level of service that the staff offers. The tourism and hospitality sector demands top-notch service due to its ever-changing nature and evolving client expectations (Wondimun, 2025).

Human resource management (HRM) consists of the strategies and procedures required to address management problems related to personnel matters (Alimardonov, 2022). The worth of any business is mostly determined by the factors including training, recruiting, assessing, rewarding employees in this sector as well as creating a safe, fair, moral workplace. It highlights how important individuals and their knowledge are for the company's successful functioning, efficient management, creative initiatives, and client relations, all of which have an impact on the customer experience. These organizations invest in education, hire qualified workers, systemize evaluation process, and focus on constant improvement in order to preserve and maintain the intellectual capital value general quality of their business. Organizations can indirectly promote productivity through a culture of continuous improvement by providing employees with the opportunity to effectively train and develop them (Tran, Phan, & Hyugen, 2025). Modern approaches to management emphasize the importance of employers, as well as the influence of psychological factors - such as abilities, goals, motives, and expectations - on the successful functioning of a business. Human resource management (HRM) consists of a set of procedures and guidelines which are related to effectively managing employee tasks (Alimardonov, 2022).

1.2 Problem statement and research gaps

In every field, but especially in tourism, the human factor plays a vital role. Nonetheless, some issues still exist that must be resolved in order to increase the level of tourists' experiences visiting a certain city or a country. Proper preparation and training are needed to complete this task. There is still a lack of professionalism and strategic leadership in tourism's human resources management practices. Low wages, excessive working hours, limited promotion opportunities, and ineffective training and development programs are still determined as employees' challenges in a workplace. Furthermore, high staff turnover in this industry is also a result of poor work-life balance and an imbalance between professional and personal responsibilities and obligations. Implementing structured planning of the workforce, wisely defining responsibilities and expectations from the work, and establishing clear career pathways in all departments of the organization are imperative for addressing these issues constructively (Katoch, 2017). HR managers' responsibilities are constantly moving from routine administrative and logistical duties to more strategic duties inside businesses. (Tang, Bai, & Cui, 2022). Regardless of these advancements, many HR practices still use conventional inefficient and outdated approaches. According to Tang et al. (2022) a significant amount of the research is based on limited data sources, such short interviews and limited surveys, which hardly reveal true demands of a company. As a consequence, many businesses struggle to identify and support talented workers. In tourism industry, such incompetence in HR sphere negatively impacts on quality of service and overall tourist experience. Thus, implementing efficient HR systems and strategies, linking employee skills to visitor expectations, is an important element (Tang, Bai, & Cui, 2022).

1.3 The purpose and objective of the study

The primary objective of this study is to examine the relationship between human resource management (HRM) techniques and the quality standards of the visitor experience across various places. To be more precise, this research investigates the impact practices, such as training, motivation, and employee management, contribute to aspects influencing tourist satisfaction, and, without any doubt, proposes several recommendations to improve problematic areas that have a detrimental effect on the tourist experience quality.

1.4 Research Questions

1. What HRM practices are most commonly used in the tourism industry?
2. What is the relationship between core HRM practices and tourism experience quality?
3. Do employee performance and job satisfaction influence tourist satisfaction?
4. What suggestions could be given to enhance a more beneficial tourist experience by enhancing the quality of human resource management (HRM)?

1.5. Significance of the study

This study intends to provide significant insights into human resource management practices that are currently being used to boost tourist satisfaction. Previous studies emphasized economic and sustainable factors of tourism rather than the role of the human factor - the employees who are in direct contact with customers. The findings will enrich the literature and knowledge regarding the strategic importance of HRM in the tourism industry. The study will help uncover the mechanism by which HR initiatives focused on engagement stimulate knowledge sharing, strengthen loyalty, and retain valuable employees. This, in turn, generates customer-focused behavior, leading to increased customer satisfaction (Sanni, 2020).

1.6. Definition of terms and concepts

Human resource management (HRM): A strategic, holistic and systematic approach to the recruitment, professional development and well-being of an organization's employees (ARMSTRONG & TAYLOR, 2014)

Tourism industry: The system of transport, service, manufacturing, retail, entertainment and other enterprises and organizations of government and civil administration, institutions of science and education, which directly or indirectly create and implement a tourism product (Yermachenko & Korzhylov, 2015)

Tourist experience: A traveller's personal and vivid impression of a destination, which is formed by their emotions, perceptions, and interactions with people and services.

Employee motivation: Internal desire and interest of employees to perform their tasks with enthusiasm and responsibility, contributing to the achievement of the organization's goals.

Service quality: The level of excellence of a company's services, determined by the degree to which they meet or exceed customer expectations based on criteria such as reliability, responsiveness, confidence, attention to needs, and material characteristics (Singh, et al., 2023)

Satisfaction of tourists: The degree of positive emotions that travellers have when comparing their expectations with actual experience or the results of the trip (Rondonuwu & Mandagi, 2023)

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The link between human resource management (HRM) practices and tourist satisfaction has been attracting more concern during the entire research work. In this second chapter, a broad literature review will be presented, outlining the import of the study, describing the theoretical framework and reviewing past research on the subject. The tourism market is a multicultural

field composed of various elements and professions, requiring different skills and knowledge levels. The structure of the market (large multinational businesses and small the business entities) determines different strategies for training, development, and promotion. Furthermore, the interconnected nature of tourism destinations, coupled with challenges related to leadership, ownership, and seasonal demand, highlights the importance of human resource management (HRM) for improving efficiency, service quality, and sustainable growth in the tourism sector.

2.2 Theoretical background

There is a big number of explanations of the concept “HRM” in the journal, books and articles, and also it is explained in a different way, the real meaning is identical. For instance, in the second edition of the book called “Human Resource Management” HRM is defined as a strategic and adaptive process that encompasses the selection, development, motivation and organization of personnel in accordance with the overall goals of the company (Collings, Wood, & Szamosi, 2019). However, this is not a single explanation for this term; there are different points and perspectives also. According to Boxall & Purcell (2016), human resource management is the process by which management develops personnel and the qualities necessary for the successful functioning of the organization. Moreover, there are five main practices of human resource management: recruitment and selection of personnel, training and development, performance appraisal and management, reward system, and employee participation in the organization's activities, the concepts of which will be elaborated on.

Recruitment and selection practices are often the starting point for organizational success within human resource management, as they can improve the overall performance of a company: recruitment involves the process of attracting candidates, while selection involves analyzing applicants and deciding whether they meet requirements (Boselie, 2014). Training and development programs help organizations develop employees' interpersonal and professional skills and modify their behavior to improve performance at the individual, team, and organizational levels (Mansour, 2013). Performance management is an ongoing organizational process that encompasses various activities to determine and evaluate the performance of individuals and teams in order to achieve business goals (Albrecht, Bakker, Gruman, Macey, & Saks, 2015). When it comes to performance appraisal, it is a regular procedure in which an employee's performance is assessed against predetermined standards and indicators.

Maslow's hierarchy of needs helps us better understand this research because it shows that when employees feel their needs are truly met, they become more motivated and perform much more effectively. Maslow presents his hierarchy as a pyramid (attached below), showing that basic needs must be met before a person can progress to higher ones. Maslow argued that failure to satisfy a need at any level blocks progression to the next stage (Rasli, Bashir, & Abu-Hussin, 2022).

Figure 1. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs¹

Motivating employees is very crucial for organization because it leads to employee satisfaction and employee retention. Many scholars argued about the importance of encouraging employees to increase organizational performances and as did Herzberg. His theory, known as Herzberg's two-factor theory, states that feelings of satisfaction and dissatisfaction with work are formed differently. Intrinsic factors such as recognition and one's own achievements are indeed motivating, while extrinsic factors-salary, comfort in the workplace-only help to avoid dissatisfaction, but do not inspire in themselves (Peramatzis & Galanakis, 2022). In fact, this theory was influenced by Maslow's theory and researched further. Motivation is a need for any company and the leaders and managers are responsible to maintain it in work. However, this is not solely about the financial rewards or comfortable environment for employees but also non-financial rewards. Staff should be view as an important resource or personality, capable of developing and acquiring new skills for the future. Investments in training and strengthening competencies increase the value of an organization's human capital. Furthermore, such development fosters greater engagement, trust, and sustained commitment among employees, and this as a result can lead to higher tourist satisfaction, as these two are interconnected.

Another concept in the service industry is the "service profit chain" (SPC). It demonstrates the connection between a company's internal processes and its external results, with employee satisfaction, loyalty, and performance being key factors linking the quality of internal and external service. According to professors Hogleve, Iseke and Derfuss (2021) customer satisfaction and loyalty serve as intermediary variables between the quality of external service and the organization's financial performance. The model includes three main components:

1. internal marketing, focusing on employee service and behavior;
2. external marketing, focused on customer experience;
3. company performance, measured by revenue growth and profitability.

Thus, in the tourism and hospitality industries, employees are the primary source of excellent service. When their needs are met (according to Maslow), their work is fulfilling (according to Herzberg), and their goals are clear and achievable, they become more engaged and motivated.

¹ Note. (McLeod, 2025)

The Service-profit chain model shows that such engagement makes tourists satisfied, repeat customers, and willing to recommend the company, which positively impacts its bottom line

2.3. Previous studies

A lot of literature exists in the field connecting tourism and HRM and **previous** research is essential for any dissertation, article or thesis, so it is reviewed and described in this section. This report provides various sources that should be relied upon to clarify some important aspects of this study. The main reason for this is that it lays the foundation for new research and helps identify existing gaps that were previously undiscovered or simply overlooked. Secondary data analysis can also help formulate hypotheses during the research process, but only primary data can confirm or refute them. Analyzing the work of previous authors and scholars can pave the way for a high-quality dissertation and a well-organized research project. It is clear that tourism as a service industry and tourists are key points of contact, and human resource management is an integral part here.

Due to intensifying global competition and increasing customer expectations, the competitive advantage of businesses and destinations in the tourism and accommodation sector and their ability to provide quality goods and services will depend on the human resources factor. The ability to recruit highly qualified employees and maximize their contribution to the firm plays a key role in this process (Chow, Haddad, & Singh, 2007). Some of the high-performance work practices commonly discussed in the human resources literature are self-managed teams, decentralized decision-making, employee empowerment, open communication, information sharing, flexible working conditions/job assignments, performance-based pay, rewards and incentives, training programs to develop knowledge/skills and abilities, selection based on person-job-organization fit, attitude assessment, job design, grievance procedures, employee-management participation programs, integrated selection and hiring procedures, career progression, and comprehensive employee participation in decision-making processes (Karatepe, 2013). The literature also provides examples of various HR management systems and practices in areas such as performance improvement, reward systems, and training. Key areas include recruitment and selection, training and development, and compensation and benefits. These include improving communication, empowering employees, and evaluating their performance. Hiring the right people, supporting service managers, creating opportunities for employee participation and initiative, providing systematic support to employees, and strategies for retaining valuable employees also play an important role. Special attention is also paid to developing loyalty, treating employees with respect, and ensuring fair pay (Kuslavan, Kuslavan, Ilhan, & Buyruk, 2010). Therefore, in order to guarantee the successful and sustainable growth of the industry, it is highly important for managerial staff draw in qualified people. By doing so, they not only give the business a competitive advantage, but also create a strong connection between country's overall socioeconomic development and human development.

The success of the hospitality industry is mainly based upon how happy or how valued the guests feel about the services provided by hotels. Developing strategic human resources development (HRD), is an essential component to the hospitality industry, in order to provide the best service possible to our guest and ensure that we provide the highest degree of customer satisfaction. In addition to developing HRD strategies, many companies implement training and development to increase employees' skills and professionalism as well as improve their knowledge; both contribute to employee performance and ultimately the quality of service. Corporate training is one of the most successful forms of employee training and development, which allows employees to continue to learn and grow throughout their careers and prepares

them to handle the constant changes in today's workplace (Waqanimaravu & Arasanmi, 2020). Training and continuing education of employees is an investment in the success and efficiency of your business. In the hospitality industry, providing great service and achieving exceptional customer satisfaction can be accomplished by implementing regular team and individualized training programs. Training employees on a consistent basis will greatly contribute to increased employee productivity, improved service quality, and create opportunities for growth that will help to strengthen your competitive position (Dhar, 2015). Without adequate employee training, organizations are at risk of providing poor service quality and therefore losing the competitive edge needed to satisfy the needs of their tourists. Employee training provides employees with the opportunity to improve their professional knowledge and skills. Organizations benefit from training employees by allowing them to keep up-to-date with the changing demands of their job, improve efficiency and effectiveness, and update and adapt employee behavior. Ultimately, training is intended to support employees in acquiring the competencies, attitudes and skills required to achieve current and future professional goals. There are a variety of ways to accomplish this, such as formal and informal programs, on-the-job and off-the-job training, and professional development initiatives. As the corporate environment continues to evolve, training has become an essential tool for organizations to ensure long-term sustainability and achieve their desired objectives. Research shows that these initiatives positively impact on businesses, as they develop abilities related to profession and enhance performance (Lee, 2012). While there exist an abundance of research discussing the connection between employee training and service quality within the hospitality and tourism industry, there remains a large gap in the area of research that examines this relationship. There exists a considerable number of studies examining the relationship between training and service quality, but fail to consider other relevant variables that may impact the relationship. In addition, there are a substantial number of studies that do not investigate the relationship between training and service quality directly. While prior research has examined the effect of training on service quality, the current body of knowledge does not provide a comprehensive understanding of the ways in which training affects service quality. For instance, although Shen & Tang's (2018) study demonstrated the influence of individual characteristics related to the delivery of training on service quality, they did not examine all key elements associated with the training process. These gaps limit our ability to develop a comprehensive understanding of the effects of employee training on service quality in the hospitality industry. Additionally, the industry poses significant issues regarding the quality of the training being provided. As noted from the various sources referenced above, the marketplace is flooded with suppliers providing low quality or non-relevant courses, and/or training individuals who lack qualifications for the job simply to obtain subsidies. Although better quality training will certainly result in improved quality and contribute to the professionalization of the industry, it does not address the long-term issues such as; attracting qualified employees due to low unemployment rates, and retaining qualified employees once hired despite quality training programs. As mentioned by a previous participant, with the low unemployment rates currently experienced, companies are finding it difficult to hire and retain qualified employees, regardless of the quality of their training programs. Further, outdated training materials and overly generic modules pose yet another challenge to the effective training of employees (Whitelaw, Barron, Bultjens, Cairncross, & Davidson, 2009).

Undoubtedly, the primary objective of any business organization is to achieve long-term growth. To be competitive and stay up-to-date enough in this in today's extremely unstable and expanding business environment, companies have to be agile, flexible, and innovative. A key

ingredient in this recipe is a positive and strong relationship between employees and organizations. Employees play a vital role in creation of products and delivering the services because they offer and implement changes from, put new ideas into action, add value, and improve efficiency of operation from their own perspectives. All of this paves the way for the company's future growth and sustainability at the same time (Perić, Gašić, Stojiljković, & Nešić, 2018). As employee performance is deemed to be an important factor in maintaining customer satisfaction in the hospitality industry, evaluating it can reveal vital aspects of tourist satisfaction. However, to what extent the employees are satisfied with their job determines to what extent the tourists are satisfied from the service. If employees feel undervalued or undertrained, this can have adverse impact on the quality of services and products offered by them, and consequently, reducing visitor satisfaction (Vrtiprah & Sladoljev, 2012). Hotels that offer compensation, reputational value, and competitive benefits are more likely to retain their employees for longer periods. Job satisfaction is proportional to the extent of employee's enjoyment with their work and feeling of appreciation for their contributions. These employees are often the most productive and valuable. Overall job happiness and satisfaction reflect an employee's comfort in the work environment. This affects their motivation, ability to achieve goals, and team spirit in general. As a result, employees who are satisfied with their working conditions tend to stay with the company longer (Harit & K., 2025). Job satisfaction is defined as an employee's positive attitude toward their work, which is formed by evaluating various aspects of it. If a person is satisfied with their job, they will have a positive attitude toward it and by contrary, low job satisfaction will lead to a negative attitude toward their job (Robbins & Judge, 2012). This was similar to the view of Sutrisno (2017) who stated that those employees who show a positive attitude toward their work are the ones who are highly satisfied. There's also an English term related to this field of ergonomics, which derives from the Greek words "ergon" and "nomos," which both mean labor and law. Essentially, it's the "science of labor" or "labor law" (Carvalho & Soares, 2012). In fact, this term is closely linked to employee performance and job satisfaction. While ergonomics can benefit many industries, the tourism industry, which requires significant physical and mental effort, has not yet fully recognized its importance. Therefore, it is crucial to integrate ergonomic principles into this industry to make employees' work more comfortable and efficient (Dul & Neumann, 2009). However, while researching these resources related to employee performance and its link to the tourist satisfaction, some gaps have been identified. In my opinion, some experts (Perić et al., 2018; Dul & Neumann, 2009; Carvalho & Soares, 2012) who have researched and analyzed various concepts such as ergonomics, innovation, and job satisfaction in general have discussed these concepts only in theory, but their work provides virtually no empirical data on tourism. It would have been better to include some references when analyzing real hotels, restaurants, and travel agencies. More specifically, data on actual employee productivity and its connection to actual levels of tourist satisfaction were lacking. Moreover, most studies (Harit & K., 2025 and Robbins & Judge, 2012) link job satisfaction to compensation, job attitudes, comfort, and benefits employees receive at work. However, there are other important factors that have not been analyzed, such as work-life balance, stress, burnout, and management neglect. By incorporating these factors into the assessment of overall employee job satisfaction, we will obtain a clearer picture of its connection with customer satisfaction.

Organizations began raising the standards of their service since the tourism industry has been expanding at a fast pace throughout the world. The ability of service or a product to meet or

exceed the customer expectation can be referred to as quality. For organizations to achieve this, it is required to have a clear understanding of the service aspects that customers find value in and contribute to their satisfaction together with loyalty. This important management tool, precisely service quality, enables companies to assess and oversee services from the customer's point of view. On the other hand, quality assurance can be also described as a collection of planned and systematic procedures which are designed to deliver goods and services that are going to satisfy certain customer needs and expectations. Strict quality control of products and services, as well as quality assurance at the delivery stage, are two critical components of an organization's procedures necessary for effective quality assurance. Regular measurement and control activities typically contribute to the improvement of these processes (Evans & Lindsay, 2010). The concept of continuous improvement is, definitely, related to the term quality management (QM). It should be considered as a dynamic process with the idea of constant improvement and innovation, rather than fixed resource or asset. This approach focuses on methodological revision and continuous evaluation, is applied within a structural system, and utilizes exact tools and techniques (European Parliament, Committee on Transport and Tourism, 2007). Another appropriate definition for the quality in hospitality and tourism sector can be the constant provision of goods and services to specific customers. Offering high-quality services in a quickly developing tourism industry on an international level is one of the difficulties tourism managers encounter, even though there are various tools and systems for measuring service quality. For managers it becomes a need to identify cost and efficiency variables to prioritize quality improvement inside their organizations (Kapiki, 2012). However, even though a lot of research on the quality of tourism services have been conducted, there is no any deep and explanatory evaluation of the literature. For instance, Park and Jeong (2019) mentioned in their works that thematic linkages, changing research trends, and a comprehensive knowledge structure of service quality in tourism are not captured by prior research, which mostly focuses on traditional measurement models and limited bibliometric or citation-based methodologies. Moreover, most of the methods discussed in the literature focused primarily on traditional measurements. However, as we live in the modern information age, research is also needed on modern approaches to analyzing the relationship between service quality and tourist satisfaction. These could include customer reviews on social media, real-time service monitoring, etc. Last but not least, there was a lack of research assessing the customer perspective. Specifically, while research focused on how to meet or exceed customer expectations, it didn't discuss the sources, differences, and changes in these expectations. People from different countries and with different traditions are likely to have different expectations, how they are formed, what triggered them to expect certain things, or how these expectations have changed over time. Thus, link between service quality and tourist satisfaction has yet to be analyzed.

Productivity has become a key factor in maintaining the competitiveness of organizations, ensuring their success in this new global economy. Thus, productivity plays a vital role in every organization and is a key variable of interest to most researchers (Imran, Majeed, & Ayub, 2015). Ineffective human resource management practices are the most important factors determining employee productivity (Zheng & Lamond, 2010). Furthermore, human resource management experts also find a positive correlation with employee performance. Beyond the size and nature of the business, employee attitudes and decisions are also factors that determine an organization's success. Thus, many organizations understand that human resource management (HRM) practices should be used in performance evaluations, as improving HR practices will ultimately improve employee productivity (Hee & Jing, 2018).

All things considered from a review of previous research, it can be concluded that human resource management (HRM) is a critical factor which determines service quality, employee performance, and customer satisfaction in the tourism and hospitality industry. Existing literature notes that human resource management practices, namely recruitment, training, performance management, and reward systems, positively influence organizational productivity and competitiveness. Skilled and motivated employees continue to be a key source of competitive advantage in the tourism sector. However, even though there has been extensive research in this area, there are still gaps that do not cover some important factors. Many studies examine human resource management and training practices separately but not combined to have a clear view of how these combinations influence service quality and tourist satisfaction. Furthermore, there is a scarcity of empirical evidence from real-life tourism organizations and research is mostly used as a theory only. Others factors, such as stress, burnout, work-life balance and depression have not been included on the list to analyze their impact on employee performance and job satisfaction. In addition, research on the service quality still depends on conventional measuring techniques rather than modern ways including contemporary data sources and changing consumer expectations. Overall, these works offer strong theoretical framework, but it lacks an integrated empirical approach to create a link between employee well-being, service quality, HRM practices and tourist satisfaction. These research gaps emphasize the importance for further investigations that is this study aims to conduct.

Based on all these findings and theoretical frameworks, following hypotheses came up:

H1: The relationship between human resource management practices (training, motivation, employee management) and employee motivation to deliver high-quality service to tourists

Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant correlation between HRM practices and employee motivation to deliver high-quality service in tourism industry.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): There is significant correlation between HRM practices and employee motivation to deliver high-quality service in tourism industry.

H2: The relationship between service quality and tourist satisfaction in tourism sector

Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant association between quality of service provided to tourists and their satisfaction in tourism sector.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): There is a significant association between quality of service provided to tourists and their satisfaction in tourism sector.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This study aims to understand and analyse the link between HRM practices (recruitment and selection, training and development, performance management, rewarding and etc.). Due to this, the purpose of third chapter (methodology) is the explanation of the way the research has been conducted. It describes research design, method, sampling population and limitations of the survey.

3.2 Research design

In order to achieve the objectives of this research, two surveys were conducted: a questionnaire for hospitality sector employees and separate questionnaire for tourists. Quantitative research was chosen for this methodology since this standardization enables the collection of accurate responses from a large number of respondents. The data collection process was undertaken online using the “Google Form” tool and distributed to regional hotels and restaurants in the city Samarkand, Republic of Uzbekistan. The primary reason is the limited ability of the researcher to go beyond the city to collect the responses. Questionnaire designed for employees consisted of 13 questions (appendix 1), while the tourists’ questionnaire consisted of 5 questions. (appendix 2) The former collected 65 responses, while the later collected 67 responses. Moreover, both questionnaires contained Likert scale and multiple-choice question types to assess the real-world relationship between these two variables: HRM practices and tourist satisfaction levels.

3.3 Research method

The primary data were collected from 4th to 10th of January 2026 in Samarkand hotels and restaurants, as well as from tourists. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire through both face-to-face and online distribution. Some employees of hotels and restaurants were asked to fill in the survey at their workplaces, and they had access to the survey through a link that was sent to them, other employees were asked to do so by receiving a message requesting them to complete the survey for educational purposes. When it comes to tourists, I visited tourist spots in order to ask visitors to take part in the survey. Additionally, some local guides helped to distribute the questionnaire to a wider group of tourists. Participation was not mandatory, but they were politely asked to volunteer.

3.4 Population Sampling

The target audience for this study consists of hospitality sector employees and guests/tourists. For this study, purposive and convenience sampling methods were used. Employees and managers in this industry were chosen to participate in this research due to the fact that they have relevant knowledge and experience and are actively involved in human resource procedures, which is suitable for the purposive sampling category. For tourists, convenience sampling method was used because I chose guests from some touristic locations randomly who were available or easy to reach at that moment.

3.5 Limitations and Weaknesses of Method and Sample

Although this study and its research were designed professionally, there are still some limitations that need to be taken into account. First of all, this empirical research is limited to Samarkand city (Republic of Uzbekistan), even though this study focuses on HRM and tourist experience on a global concept. This occurs because of my time constraints and geographical location. Secondly, responses can be accurate only to this region, as the process and practices in other regions may vary from Samarkand. Thirdly, some responses can be considered biased as

they have been collected through quantitative method rather than qualitative approaches, which is considered to collect deeper insights in this process.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to outline the key findings of the study, provide clear picture of results, and discuss the final results on the basis of primarily conducted survey together with secondary data provided. Descriptive statistics and various types of inferential statistics were used for calculating the data that was submitted by 132 respondents in total (65 employees and 67 tourists). Patterns for variables, such as human resource management practices, motivation, service quality and tourist satisfaction, emerged from the descriptive data and ordinal regression analysis. Computer program, IBM SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) Statistics, was used to process the statistical data of this research.

4.2 Analysis of employees' survey results

In this section responses collected from employees working in the hospitality and tourism sphere are analyzed. The purpose is to examine employees' demographics, training practices, motivation, satisfaction and their contribution to the level of service quality

Figure 2. Profile of employee respondents²

The presented clustered bar chart shows the interaction between demographic and professional profiles of the respondents working in tourism sector. Front desk/reception workers seem to have high turnover rate as most of them worked less than 1 year (11%), and only 4 % worked 4-5 years and this duration is the limit in this working sphere. Employees working in housekeeping and other jobs have relatively balanced distribution of experience years ranging from less than 1 year up to more than 5 years. Food and beverage sector displays mid-career level rather than other sectors since 8 percent of respondents have been working for 1-3 years and approximately 6.5 percent of them have been working for 4-5 years in this sector. Managers' category demonstrates the highest level of seniority with the notable peak of percentage in working experience with more than 5 years, which is calculated for more than 15 %.

² Author's elaboration based on the survey

Figure 3. Training practices

The given bar chart demonstrates the employees' perception of training and actual training experience. It is clear that in most of the cases employees received formal training in their workplaces and their perception value about this process is also high. The majority (approximately 22%) of employees, who received formal training claim, and even the minority (3%), who did not receive training, claim that training is extremely relevant. Proportion of employee responses estimating the value of training as very relevant, moderately relevant, slightly relevant is also considered to be high. When it comes to the category of employees not sharing this view and finding training as not relevant at all, it is the least populated. Only 7% and 1% of those received training and did not respectively underestimate this practice.

Which factors motivate workers in this industry? (you can choose several options)

65 ответов

Figure 4. Motivation factors of employees

The horizontal chart shows the factors which motivate workers the most according to their responses. For this question in the survey employees had right to choose several options at once, and it is clear that all HRM factors play significant role in employee motivation. Surprisingly, the biggest motivation for workers in tourism industry is considered to be salary and rewards together with promotional opportunities, both of which were chosen 43 times, each making up 66,2%. No less important factor according to employees is training and professional development which made up almost 60%. Other factors, such as recognition and respect from management, job stability and security, communication and teamwork (positive atmosphere), are also deemed to be important, constituting 46,2%, 47,7%, 50,5% respectively.

Table 1. Frequency analysis of the relevance of stress or burnout to the service quality

Stress or burnout among employees affects service quality provided to tourists ?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	disagree	3	4,5	4,6	4,6
	neutral	9	13,4	13,8	18,5
	agree	23	34,3	35,4	53,8
	strongly agree	30	44,8	46,2	100,0
	Total	65	97,0	100,0	
Missing	System	2	3,0		
Total		67	100,0		

The results of the survey indicate on the dependency of service quality on the employee mental conditions. According to the majority agreed or strongly agreed (35,4% and 46,2% respectively) that stress or burnout among employees negatively affect the quality of service provided to tourists. Only a small proportion of employees (4,6%) disagreed with this statement while roughly 14% of respondents remained in neutral position. This indicates that most employees recognize the importance of controlling stress and burnout in order to keep the customer service level high enough to satisfy customers.

Table 2. Frequency analysis of most important HR practices for improving service quality

Which one of HR practices improves the service quality in tourism sector?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	staff training	22	32,8	33,8	33,8
	motivation and rewards	22	32,8	33,8	67,7
	communication and teamwork	11	16,4	16,9	84,6
	employee selection and recruitment	10	14,9	15,4	100,0
	Total	65	97,0	100,0	
Missing	System	2	3,0		
Total		67	100,0		

Data from the tourists’ survey shows the most important HR practice tendency to improve the quality of the service in tourism sector according to employees. With the frequency of 22 both and a combined percentage of valid responses 67,6%, employees consider staff training and motivation and rewards practices as the most important one for enhancing service quality. Following this, communication and teamwork was selected 11 times and valid percentage is calculated for almost 17%. Among these practices, employee selection and recruitment were seen as least important and is accounted for slightly exceeding 15%.

4.3 Analysis of tourists’ survey results

In this part responses collected from tourists, visiting Samarkand and using tourism facilities, are analyzed. The purpose is to identify and evaluate the staff attitude and professionalism towards tourists, in general, the overall experience of tourists.

Table 3. Frequency analysis of staff attitude evaluation

How would you rate the staff attitude during your trip to Uzbekistan?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	neutral	11	16,4	16,4	16,4
	positive	26	38,8	38,8	55,2
	very positive	30	44,8	44,8	100,0
	Total	67	100,0	100,0	

The data presented in the table shows the evaluation of staff attitude to tourists during their trip to Uzbekistan in a form of frequency analysis. It is clear that tourists received an exceptional high level of satisfaction when it comes to staff attitude, with the majority of respondents (almost a half) highlighting it as “very positive”, and nearly 40% considering as “positive”. Only 16,4 percent of tourists expressed “neutral” opinion. Notable, even though there have been negative options, no any tourist evaluated staff attitude as “negative” or “very negative”. Thus, high frequency of positive replies and absence of negative feedbacks indicate that employees are trained and move towards professionalism.

Table 4. Frequency analysis of staff professionalism

To what extent were the staff professional in tourism sector?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	slightly professional	4	6,0	6,0	6,0
	Moderate	13	19,4	19,4	25,4
	Professional	24	35,8	35,8	61,2
	Very professional	26	38,8	38,8	100,0
	Total	67	100,0	100,0	

The given data from the table shows the tourists’ evaluation of staff professionalism in tourism sector in Uzbekistan. Nearly 40% and 36% of respondents rated staff as “very professional” and “professional”, respectively. Regarding frequency of these proportions, totally it is about 50 respondents out of 67. Tourists viewing employees as “moderate” in terms of professionalism are constituted one-fifth. Conversely, only 4 respondents (6%) evaluated them as “slightly professional”. Notably, no single negative feedback, highlighted as “not professional”, was received. Overall, this survey shows a high rate of positive results regarding the professionalism of employees in tourism sector.

4.4 Hypotheses testing

As it was mentioned in chapter 2, two hypotheses came out from previous findings and gaps that have been analyzed above. For testing these hypotheses, linear regression analysis has been brought.

While testing first hypothesis related to the relationship between human resource management practices and employee motivation to deliver high-quality service to tourists, following data came up:

Table 5. Anova results of regression analysis for testing H1

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	35,112	6	5,852	7,551	,000 ^b
	Residual	44,950	58	,775		
	Total	80,062	64			

a. Dependent Variable: To what extent do employees feel motivated to deliver high-quality service to the tourists?

b. Predictors: (Constant), Do you agree with the statement: "Management pays enough attention to HR practices to enhance tourist experience in tourism sector"?, Do you think formal training is relevant for working with tourists in tourism industry?, Stress or burnout among employees affects service quality provided to tourists ?, How do you evaluate working hours in this sector?, How satisfied are you with the salary in the tourism industry?, Do employees in this sector feel valued or appreciated by management?

This table represents linear regression analysis that was conducted to test the relationship between human resource management practices and employee motivation to deliver high-quality service to tourists. While HRM practices, such as training, management attention, salary satisfaction, working hours and atmosphere, stress or burnout, appreciation, were taken as independent variable, employee motivation was regarded as dependent variable. According to ANOVA results, the regression model is statistically significant because $F=7.551$, $p < 0.001$.

This proves that set of HRM practices substantially influence the variations in the motivation of employees for delivering the service. As the significance value is lower than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis (H0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H1). Thus, the findings confirm the notion that there is a significant correlation between HRM practices and employee motivation to deliver high-quality service to tourists in tourism industry.

While testing second hypothesis related to the relationship between service quality and tourist satisfaction in tourism sector, following data came up:

Table 6. Anova results of regression analysis for testing H2

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27,963	3	9,321	29,615	<,001 ^b
	Residual	19,828	63	,315		
	Total	47,791	66			

a. Dependent Variable: overall, to what extent were you 4with service provided by employees?

b. Predictors: (Constant), How would you rate the staff attitude during your trip to Uzbekistan?, To what extent did the employee behaviour influence your overall travel experience and satisfaction level?, To what extent were the staff professional in tourism sector?

This table represents linear regression analysis that was conducted to test the relationship between service quality and tourist satisfaction in tourism sector. Here the tourist satisfaction was regarded as dependent variable whereas indicators of service quality, such as staff attitude, staff professionalism, employee behavior, were used as independent variable. According to ANOVA results, linear regression model is considered to be statistically significant, because $F=29.615$, $p<0,001$. By this, it has become clear that there is a significant influence of quality of service provided on tourist satisfaction. In this case, null hypothesis (H0) is rejected and alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Therefore, there is a strong correlation between tourist satisfaction and the quality of service they receive in tourism industry.

4.5 Discussion

In this section, main results of the survey in relation to previously mentioned literature, theoretical framework and research questions are discussed.

The results of the survey that was conducted with the employees reveal that the HRM practices play an important role in enhancing the motivation of employees to provide better or high-quality service to the customers. This theory has been proven with the help of regression model analysis as well. By these findings, we can answer the first and second questions of survey that were highlighted in chapter 1, and prove not only effectiveness of these HRM practices in tourism sector, but also their significant impact on employee performance and behavior. Notably, these results match with the previous studies brought in chapter 2 , which stated that training opportunities, working condition, attentive and supportive management and fair treatment and compensation shape the employee motivation together with performance. There have also been mentioned about the importance of employee well-being in service-oriented industries. According to survey results , majority of employees agreed on the negative impact of stress and burnout on the effectiveness and quality of the service that, consequently, harm the tourist experience. Moreover, this result is also consistent with the Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs which claims that before workers can perform at a high level, firstly, their basic needs,

such as fair pay, job security, good working environment, must be met. The same case with Herzberg's Two-Factor theory which states that both intrinsic (recognition, appreciation, support) and extrinsic (salary, working hours) factors influence on motivation level of employees.

When it comes to the analysis of testing the Hypothesis 2, the survey results of the tourists and regression model analysis showed a strong and statistically relationship between service quality and tourist satisfaction. Tourists' satisfaction is hugely influenced by the key variables, such as staff attitude, professionalism and staff behavior. It has also become clear that direct interaction with employees have significant impact on tourists' experiences. Most importantly, these data support The Service-Profit Chain theory from previous studies, which notes that motivated staff, improved service quality, increased customer satisfaction are the results of effective internal management. In short, the results of this study offer empirical evidence of this chain in tourism industry in Samarkand, showing that better visitor experiences are strongly linked with the investment in human resources.

4.6 Conclusion

This chapter has sought to outline empirical evidences of the study with the help of data that was collected from both employees and tourists. Descriptive statistics and various types of inferential statistics were used with the help of SPSS in order to test the relationship between variables of two hypotheses: HRM practices, staff motivation, service quality and tourist satisfaction. The findings revealed a strong correlation between these variables for both hypotheses and also answered to the research questions. To be more precise, results of the study demonstrate how important human resource management is to improving service quality and , consequently, tourist satisfaction in tourism industry.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION

5.1 Introduction

This chapter concludes all the results of this study and concludes based on the empirical findings. It highlights the importance of the research conducted to address the existed problem constructively. Moreover, it brings implications for practical applications and future studies, gives basic recommendations for organizations working in tourism sector, discusses the limitations of this study, and finally, concludes with final remarks.

5.2 Significance of the findings

The findings of this study are very significant as the results of analyses provide empirical evidence about the human resource management practices and how their implications can change the situation in industry by improving service quality and tourist satisfaction levels. Besides the surveys conducted to know the opinions of employees and tourists and their results in the form of descriptive analyses, regression model also brought clear picture of the findings. First of all, they demonstrated that HRM practices, such as training, motivation, management support, pleasant working conditions, have a statistically significant influence on employee motivation to deliver high-quality service. Furthermore, this study reveals that indicators of service quality, such as staff attitude, professionalism, staff behavior, have statistically significant influence on tourist satisfaction. These findings support the theories brought in previous studies and highlight the importance of effective HRM practices in shaping the positive tourist experiences and also improving the quality of service in this competitive tourism industry.

5.3 Implications for practical applications and future studies

To start with implications for practical applications, this study can be used as important guidance by tourism organizations and managers. Firstly, as the study suggests, they can allocate

more investments and time on employee training and professional development, since by doing so they can enhance service quality in their organizations. Secondly, management should be attentive to the well-being of their employees and address the problems related to stress and burnout by improving working conditions and maintaining proper work-life balance. Thirdly, management should motivate their staff through fair compensation, support and recognition. These findings can serve as a guideline for struggling organizations to overcome challenge, and for well-operating organizations to continue keeping competitive positions or even design more effective strategies.

Regarding implications for future studies, through demonstrating empirical connection between HRM practices, employee motivation, service quality, and tourist satisfaction, this study adds contribution to the existing literature. Future researchers can use materials from this study to fill the gaps of existing literature, gain some insights, incorporate qualitative research or continue investigating this topic in a wider scale or other regions.

5.4 Recommendations

1. Implement regular and effective training programs for all staff in hotels and restaurants to enhance the employee knowledge, skills and professionalism by HR and management departments.
2. Raise attention to providing motivation to employees through both financial (bonuses, salary increases) and non-financial (career development opportunities, recognition programs) incentives by the side of management.
3. Maintain pleasant working conditions, by identifying and eliminating stress-related factors and this is better done by management departments mostly for reception and housekeeping departments.
4. Look for more strategic ways to align HRM practices with service quality and tourist satisfaction goals under the control of hotel managers.
5. Never leave the process without monitoring; keep continuous monitoring of service quality, and this must be controlled by quality control managers and HR specialists.

5.5 Limitations

Despite all the contributions and adequate analysis, this study has some limitations. First of all, as it has been mentioned in previous chapters, the research has been conducted only in one of regions of Uzbekistan Republic- Samarkand. This limits its opportunities to evaluate the results on a broader scale. Moreover, the survey has been conducted only in a quantitative form, which limits the participants to provide deeper insights related to the topic. Last but not least, even though the number of participants can be adequate for the statistical analysis, it can be expanded for future research works, perhaps for analyzing other regions as well.

5.6 Conclusion

All things considered, it can be concluded that the critical role of human resource management practices in enhancing tourist experience, their satisfaction, service quality and employee motivation in tourism industry has been proved. Results agreed with the hypotheses brought from the limitations and research questions of the study. It has become clear that motivated staff deliver high-quality service, which, as a result, increases tourist satisfaction. Tourism organizations can gain many benefits and competitive position, improve service quality and employee performance by strengthening their HRM department. This study provides practitioners and researchers, looking to improve service quality and sustainable development in tourism industry, with valuable insights.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Employees' Survey Questions

1. What is your current occupation?
 - front desk/reception
 - housekeeping
 - food and beverage
 - management; administration
 - other
2. How long have you worked in tourism sector?
 - less than 1 year
 - 1-3 years
 - 4-5 years
 - more than 5 years
3. Have you ever received a formal training in your workplace?
 - yes
 - no
4. Do you think formal training is relevant for working with tourists in tourism industry?
 - not relevant at all
 - slightly relevant
 - moderately relevant
 - very relevant
 - extremely relevant
5. How satisfied are you with the salary in the tourism industry?
 - satisfied
 - neutral
 - dissatisfied
6. Which factors motivate workers in this industry? (you can choose several options)
 - salary and rewards
 - recognition and respect from management
 - promotional opportunities
 - job stability and security
 - communication and teamwork (positive atmosphere)
 - training and professional development
7. How do you evaluate working hours in this sector?
 - very reasonable

-mostly reasonable

- neither reasonable nor demanding

- slightly demanding

-very demanding

8. stress or burnout among employees affects service quality provided to tourists ?

- strongly agree

-agree

-neutral

-disagree

-strongly disagree

9. Do employees in this sector feel valued or appreciated by management?

-yes

-no

10. To what extent do employees feel motivated to deliver high-quality service to the tourists?

-extremely motivated

-very motivated

-moderately motivated

-slightly motivated

-not motivated

11. Which one of HR practices improves the service quality in tourism sector?

- staff training

- motivation and rewards

- communication and teamwork

-employee selection and recruitment

12. Do you agree that staff behaviour strongly influence the overall tourist experience?

-strongly agree

-agree

-neutral

-disagree

-strongly disagree

13. Do you agree with the statement: “Management pays enough attention to HR practices to enhance tourist experience in tourism sector”?

- strongly agree

-agree

-neutral

-disagree

-strongly disagree

Appendix B: Tourists’ Survey Questions

1. How would you rate the staff attitude during your trip to Uzbekistan?

-very positive

-positive

-neutral

-negative

-very negative

2. To what extent were the staff professional in tourism sector?

- very professional
- professional
- moderate
- slightly professional
- unprofessional

3. Overall, to what extent were you with service provided by employees?

- very satisfied
- satisfied
- neutral
- lightly satisfied
- dissatisfied

4. To what extent did the employee behaviour influence your overall travel experience and satisfaction level?

- strongly influenced
- moderately influenced
- not influenced at all

5. Do you agree that staff behaviour strongly influence the overall tourist experience?

- strongly agree
- agree
- neutral
- disagree
- strongly disagree

Appendix C: Additional analysis results for hypothesis 1

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
To what extent do employees feel motivated to deliver high-quality service to the tourists?	3,75	1,118	65
Do you think formal training is relevant for working with tourists in tourism industry?	3,26	1,350	65
How satisfied are you with the salary in the tourism industry?	2,48	,615	65
How do you evaluate working hours in this sector?	3,92	,973	65
Stress or burnout among employees affects service quality provided to tourists ?	4,23	,862	65
Do employees in this sector feel valued or appreciated by management?	1,80	,403	65
Do you agree with the statement: "Management pays enough attention to HR practices to enhance tourist experience in tourism sector"?	4,09	,914	65

Correlations

		To what extent do employees feel motivated to deliver high-quality service to the tourists?	Do you think formal training is relevant for working with tourists in tourism industry?	How satisfied are you with the salary in the tourism industry?	How do you evaluate working hours in this sector?	Stress or burnout among employees affects service quality provided to tourists ?	Do employees in this sector feel valued or appreciated by management ?	Do you agree with the statement: "Management pays enough attention to HR practices to enhance tourist experience in tourism sector"?
Pearson Correlation	To what extent do employees feel motivated to deliver high-quality service to the tourists?	1,000	,147	,264	,470	,238	,374	,603
	Do you think formal training is relevant for working with tourists in tourism industry?	,147	1,000	,186	,218	,256	,213	,119
	How satisfied are you with the salary in the tourism industry?	,264	,186	1,000	,428	,261	,328	,476
	How do you evaluate working hours in this sector?	,470	,218	,428	1,000	,264	,159	,412
	Stress or burnout among employees affects service quality provided to tourists ?	,238	,256	,261	,264	1,000	,135	,290
	Do employees in this sector feel valued or appreciated by management?	,374	,213	,328	,159	,135	1,000	,602
	Do you agree with the statement: "Management pays enough attention to HR practices to enhance tourist experience in tourism sector"?	,603	,119	,476	,412	,290	,602	1,000
Sig. (1-tailed)	To what extent do employees feel motivated to deliver high-quality service to the tourists?	.	,122	,017	,000	,028	,001	,000
	Do you think formal training is relevant for working with tourists in tourism industry?	,122	.	,069	,041	,020	,045	,172
	How satisfied are you with the salary in the tourism industry?	,017	,069	.	,000	,018	,004	,000
	How do you evaluate working hours in this sector?	,000	,041	,000	.	,017	,102	,000
	Stress or burnout among employees affects service quality provided to tourists ?	,028	,020	,018	,017	.	,142	,010
	Do employees in this sector feel valued or appreciated by management?	,001	,045	,004	,102	,142	.	,000
	Do you agree with the statement: "Management pays enough attention to HR practices to enhance tourist experience in tourism sector"?	,000	,172	,000	,000	,010	,000	.
N	To what extent do employees feel motivated to deliver high-quality service to the tourists?	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
	Do you think formal training is relevant for working with tourists in tourism industry?	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
	How satisfied are you with the salary in the tourism industry?	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
	How do you evaluate working hours in this sector?	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
	Stress or burnout among employees affects service quality provided to tourists ?	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
	Do employees in this sector feel valued or appreciated by management?	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
	Do you agree with the statement: "Management pays enough attention to HR practices to enhance tourist experience in tourism sector"?	65	65	65	65	65	65	65

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,662 ^a	,439	,380	,880

a. Predictors: (Constant), Do you agree with the statement: "Management pays enough attention to HR practices to enhance tourist experience in tourism sector"?, Do you think formal training is relevant for working with tourists in tourism industry?, Stress or burnout among employees affects service quality provided to tourists ?, How do you evaluate working hours in this sector?, How satisfied are you with the salary in the tourism industry?, Do employees in this sector feel valued or appreciated by management?

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-,045	,749		-,060	,952
	Do you think formal training is relevant for working with tourists in tourism industry?	,020	,088	,025	,233	,816
	How satisfied are you with the salary in the tourism industry?	-,242	,215	-,133	-1,125	,265
	How do you evaluate working hours in this sector?	,344	,134	,300	2,575	,013
	Stress or burnout among employees affects service quality provided to tourists ?	,047	,139	,036	,339	,736
	Do employees in this sector feel valued or appreciated by management?	,178	,354	,064	,502	,618
	Do you agree with the statement: "Management pays enough attention to HR practices to enhance tourist experience in tourism sector"?	,601	,174	,491	3,455	,001

a. Dependent Variable: To what extent do employees feel motivated to deliver high-quality service to the tourists?

Appendix D: Additional analysis results for hypothesis 2

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
overall, to what extent were you 4with service provided by employees?	4,13	,851	67
How would you rate the staff attitude during your trip to Uzbekistan?	4,28	,735	67
To what extent were the staff professional in tourism sector?	4,07	,910	67
To what extent did the employee behaviour influence your overall travel experience and satisfaction level?	2,43	,633	67

Correlations

		overall, to what extent were you 4with service provided by employees?	How would you rate the staff attitude during your trip to Uzbekistan?	To what extent were the staff professional in tourism sector?	To what extent did the employee behaviour influence your overall travel experience and satisfaction level?
Pearson Correlation	overall, to what extent were you 4with service provided by employees?	1,000	,593	,711	,509
	How would you rate the staff attitude during your trip to Uzbekistan?	,593	1,000	,648	,319
	To what extent were the staff professional in tourism sector?	,711	,648	1,000	,417
	To what extent did the employee behaviour influence your overall travel experience and satisfaction level?	,509	,319	,417	1,000
Sig. (1-tailed)	overall, to what extent were you 4with service provided by employees?	.	<,001	<,001	<,001
	How would you rate the staff attitude during your trip to Uzbekistan?	,000	.	,000	,004
	To what extent were the staff professional in tourism sector?	,000	,000	.	,000
	To what extent did the employee behaviour influence your overall travel experience and satisfaction level?	,000	,004	,000	.
N	overall, to what extent were you 4with service provided by employees?	67	67	67	67
	How would you rate the staff attitude during your trip to Uzbekistan?	67	67	67	67
	To what extent were the staff professional in tourism sector?	67	67	67	67
	To what extent did the employee behaviour influence your overall travel experience and satisfaction level?	67	67	67	67

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,765 ^a	,585	,565	,561

a. Predictors: (Constant), To what extent did the employee behaviour influence your overall travel experience and satisfaction level?, How would you rate the staff attitude during your trip to Uzbekistan?, To what extent were the staff professional in tourism sector?

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,496	,434		1,143	,257
	How would you rate the staff attitude during your trip to Uzbekistan?	,240	,124	,207	1,936	,057
	To what extent were the staff professional in tourism sector?	,444	,104	,475	4,262	<,001
	To what extent did the employee behaviour influence your overall travel experience and satisfaction level?	,330	,120	,246	2,745	,008

a. Dependent Variable: overall, to what extent were you 4with service provided by employees?